

Effect of Brief Interpersonal Therapy on Depression During Pregnancy *A Randomized Clinical Trial*

Importance: Prenatal depression is common and can negatively affect both mothers and their developing fetuses. Effective and safe interventions are essential for reducing depression during pregnancy.

Objective: The study assessed the effectiveness of brief interpersonal psychotherapy (IPT) compared to enhanced usual care (EUC) in reducing depression symptoms and diagnoses in a diverse group of pregnant individuals.

Design, Settings and Participants: The randomized clinical trial, named the Care Project, involved pregnant adults with elevated depression symptoms identified during routine OB/GYN care. Participants were recruited between July 2017 and August 2021 and followed throughout pregnancy. Randomization assigned participants to either IPT or EUC for intent-to-treat analyses.

Interventions: The IPT group received an engagement session and 8 active MOMCare sessions during pregnancy. The EUC group received engagement and maternity support services.

Main Outcomes and Measures: Depression was measured using the 20-item Symptom Checklist and the Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale, along with structured clinical interviews for major depressive disorder (MDD) at baseline and the end of gestation.

Results:

- Participants: 234 individuals (115 IPT, 119 EUC). Both groups were similar in demographics, including age (~30 years) and Medicaid enrollment (~50%).
- Depression Symptom Improvement: IPT participants showed significant symptom reductions compared to EUC:
 - 20-item Symptoms Checklist (IPT: 26.7 to 13.6 vs EUC: 27.1 to 23.5).
 - Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (IPT: 11.4 to 5.4 vs EUC: 11.5 to 7.6).
- MDD Rates: By the end of pregnancy, MDD prevalence was significantly lower in the IPT group (6.1%) compared to EUC (26.1%).

Conclusion: Brief interpersonal psychotherapy during pregnancy significantly reduces depression symptoms and MDD diagnoses compared to enhanced usual care. This supports IPT as an effective intervention for prenatal depression.

Figure 1.

Illustrates the selection process of study participants, showing how eliminations were made at various stages. By including this diagram, the authors aim to demonstrate the qualification process. A significant number of individuals who did not meet the required criteria were excluded during the selection process.

The first selection phase was based on:

- Age: 18–45
- Proficiency in English
- Pregnancy at 25 weeks or less
- Singleton pregnancy
- Severe depressive symptoms
- No use of psychoactive substances
- No methadone use
- No severe medical conditions

The second selection phase was based on:

- Current or past psychosis or mania

- Ongoing cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) or interpersonal therapy (IPT)

Randomization:

Participants who met all criteria were randomly assigned to one of two groups:

1. **EUC** (Enhanced Usual Care)
2. **IPT** (Interpersonal Therapy)

Figure 2.

The Effect of Interventions on Depression Symptoms During Pregnancy

Figure 2 illustrates the impact of EUC and IPT therapies on the studied groups.

- In **Panel A**, individuals in the EUC group significantly outnumber those in the IPT group. The SCL-20 scale was used in this analysis.
- In **Panel B**, individuals in the EUC group also outnumber those in the IPT group, but to a lesser extent. The Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale was utilized in this analysis.

The study demonstrated a significant interaction between intervention and time, with a differentiated improvement in depression symptoms in the IPT group compared to the EUC group over time. The figure highlights the effect of brief interpersonal therapy on depression during pregnancy.

Figure 3.

The Effect of Interventions on the Diagnosis Rate of Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) According to DSM-5

Figure 3 depicts, using depressive symptom criteria, how the MDD diagnosis rate (in percentages) differed between groups at the start and end of the study.

- Initially, individuals in both groups exhibited high levels of depression symptoms.
- After completing the study, a significant decrease in symptoms was observed in the IPT group. However, in the EUC group, the decrease was not as pronounced.

In summary, this chart demonstrates how brief interpersonal therapy impacts depression symptoms during pregnancy.

Table 1.

The table illustrates how previous lifestyle, social behaviors, and ethnic background shaped the study participants. It characterizes the group by highlighting the shared traits of individual, unrelated women.

Table 2.

The table shows the difference in the rate of change in depression symptoms using the SCL-20 scale between the IPT and EUC groups from randomization to the end of pregnancy.

Authors:

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